

PRELIMINARY ASSESSMENT OF THE RARE EARTH ELEMENT COMPOSITION OF SHALES OF THE GONGILA FORMATION, GONGOLA BASIN NIGERIA.

¹Imagbe, O. L, ²Piwuna, R.M. and ³Egbon, W.E

^{1&2}Department of Geology and Mining, University of Jos, Nigeria.

³Raw Materials Research and Development Council, Maitama district, Abuja, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

This preliminary study was carried out on the Shales of the Cenomanian-Turonian sedimentary sequence representing the Gongila Formation of the Gongola Basin as exposed in the Ashaka Cement quarry in Gombe, northeastern Nigeria. A total of ten shale samples were collected from the outcropping sections, out of which five representative samples were subjected to instrumental Neutron Activation Analytical (INAA) methods. The results of the analysis of the shale samples shows the average composition values; La (57), Ce (89.4), Nd (34), Sm (6.94), Eu (1.52), Tb (0.66), Lu (0.42). This result however shows slightly high LREE (light rare earth elements) enrichment and relatively low HREE (heavy rare earth elements) when compared to the Post-Achean Australian Standard (PAAS). The provenance of the Shales thus may be ascribed a granitic source rock with a high proportion of plagioclase feldspars.

KEYWORDS: Rare earth, Shales, Gongila Formation, Provenance.

INTRODUCTION

Gongila formation is one of the many sedimentary formations in the Gongola sub basin of the Benue Trough (fig.1). The type locality of the Formation is well exposed in the limestone quarry of the Ashaka Cement Factory at Ashaka village in Gombe state, north eastern Nigeria (Obaje *et al*, 1999a) (fig.2).

The Formation was first named by Carter *et al* (1963) to distinguish it from the almost similar Pindiga Formation on the 'Zambuk Ridge'. It lies conformably on the Yolde formation and is one in a series of marine calcareous units deposited in the Gongola Basin during the Mid- Cretaceous worldwide transgression.

The Formation is lithologically characterized by dark carbonaceous limestones and shales, intercalated with pale limestones and shales and minor sandstones.

Popoff *et al.*, (1986), Zarboski *et al.*, (1998, 2000), Obi (1998), Obaje *et al* (1999, 2000) and Imagbe and Davou (2007) have variously carried out studies on aspects of the stratigraphy, origin, depositional environment and geological significance of the Gongila formation. However, despite these studies, none has focussed on the trace and rare element geochemistry which tend to create a lacuna in the multidisciplinary approach of investigating the formation.

Trace and rare element Geochemistry as a tool for rock provenance, depositional environment, facies and diagenetic changes has been used by many authors (Elderfield *et al* 1981; Glasby *et al* 1987; Adekeye *et al* 2007).

This preliminary study presents the rare earth element occurrence and distribution patterns in shale of the Gongila formation to provide an understanding of the environment of deposition as well as determine their source rock.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

The Gongila Formation is located within the Gongila-Gombe Sub basin of the Gongola Basin of the Upper Benue Trough, Nigeria (Popoff *et al.*, 1986).

The Upper Benue Trough was first investigated by J.D Falconar, (1911) who described some of the Cretaceous and Tertiary sedimentary formations. Stonely, (1966) and J.B Wright (1968) proposed a graben genesis related to the Cretaceous opening of the Gulf of Guinea. Burke *et al*, (1972) suggested a sea floor spreading model for the

Southern Benue Trough. Grant, (1971) characterized the Benue Basin as an aulacogen based on a triple arm rift model. All these subsequent methods imply a continental rifting for the genesis of the Benue Basin.

An outline of the major stratigraphical subdivisions of the Cretaceous to Tertiary Sedimentary formations of the Benue Trough was reported by Peters (1982), fig 2.

Fig 1; Simplified geological map showing the location of the Benue trough, its subdivisions and the Ashaka Limestone quarry

ZABORSKI <i>et al.</i> , 1997			CARTER <i>et al.</i> (1963)		POPOFF <i>et al.</i> (1986)	
GONGOLA BASIN			ZAMBUK RIDGE	CHAD BASIN	GONGOLA TROUGH (Pindiga-Gombe) (Gonggila-Gombe) Zambuk Ridge -Ashaka-	
					Chad Formation	PLEISTOCENE - PLOCENE
Kerri Kerri Formation			Kerri Kerri Formation		Biu Basalts	MIOCENE - PALEOCENE
Gombe Sandstones			Gombe Sandstones		Gombe Sandstones	U MAASTRICHTIAN
Pindiga Formation	Fika Member	CAMPANIAN	Pindiga Formation including Gulani Sandstone	Fika Shales	Pindiga Shales	CAMPANIAN
		SANTONIAN				SANTONIAN
		CONIACIAN				CONIACIAN
		UPPER TURONIAN				U M TURONIAN
	Dumbulwa/Gulani/Deba Fufani Member	MIDDLE TURONIAN			Gonggila Formation	L TURONIAN
	Kanawa Member	LOWER TURONIAN				L TURONIAN
Yolde Formation			Yolde Formation		Yolde Formation	U M L CENOMANIAN
BIMA GROUP	"Upper Bima Formation"	ALBIAN	Blima Sandstones		Blima Sandstones	U M L ALBIAN
	"Middle Bima Formation"	APTIAN	unconformity		unconformity	U M L APTIAN
	"Lower Bima Formation"	pre-APTIAN				U M L JURASSIC
+++ Crystalline basement +++			+++ Crystalline basement +++	+++ Crystalline basement +++	+++ Crystalline basement +++	+++ Crystalline basement +++
PRECAMBRIAN			PRECAMBRIAN	PRECAMBRIAN	PRECAMBRIAN	PRECAMBRIAN

Fig 2: Major stratigraphic subdivisions of the Cretaceous to Tertiary sedimentary formations of the Benue Trough, Nigeria. (Modified from Petters, 1982; Grandstein *et al.*, 2004.)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Initial fieldwork involving vertical in situ outcropping sedimentary sequence description, measurements and sampling in the Gongila Formation has earlier been carried out and reported in Imagbe and Davou (2007).

Ten shale samples were collected from the outcropping sections, out of which five representative samples were subjected to Instrumental Neutron Activation Analytical (INAA) methods. This method was chosen because of its high sensitivity and efficiency. All the analysis was carried out at the Activation Laboratory, Canada. This method involves weighing a 30g sample into specially fabricated small polyethylene vials. The sample was then irradiated with control international reference material CANMET WMS – 1 and Ni-Cr flux of $7 \times 10^{12} \text{ ncm}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the McMaster Nuclear Reactor. Following 7 day decay, the sample was measured and the Canberra Series 95 Multi-channel analyzer under computer controls (Hoffman, E. L., 1992).

The detection limit for the rare earth elements is between 0.1 and 5ppm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Field Occurrence of Shales

The Gongila Formation is lithologically characterized by dark carbonaceous limestone, calcareous shale, intercalated by pale limestone and grey shale and minor sandstones reaching a collective thickness of nearly 12 meters above ground level as observed at the type locality of the formation exposed in the limestone quarry at Ashaka. The limestone is massive and contains well preserved sections, highly fossilized with evidence of mega fossils including ammonites, bivalves, and gastropods which are abundant in the lower part of the section. Thick grey shale beds were however observed to cap the limestone sequence and thus were susceptible to varying degrees of chemical weathering, as typified by the reddish-brown iron stains on the surfaces of the shales. The shales are fissile and friable in nature. The proportion of clay, silt and carbonaceous material vary within the shale resulting in different types of wavy laminated microfabric. Diagnostic sedimentary structures within the top shales of this formation include desiccation cracks, laminations and joints.

Chemical Analyses

The results of the analysis of the five representative shale samples shows rare earth elements concentration value ranging from 0.5 to 103ppm (Table 1). The average elemental composition values are ; La (57), Ce (89.4), Nd (34), Sm (6.94), Eu (1.52), Tb (0.66), Lu (0.42). This result however show slightly high LREE (light rare earth elements) enrichment and relatively low HREE (heavy rare earth elements) when compared to the Post-Achaean Australian Standard (PAAS).

Table 1: Rare Earth Elements Composition (ppm) of Shales in the Gongila formation

Element	W1	W2	W3	W4	W5	PAAS
La	52.5	50.5	65.1	55.7	61.2	38
Ce	84	81	103	91	88	80
Nd	28	30	43	37	32	32
Sm	6.5	6.3	8.3	7.1	6.5	5.6
Eu	1.3	1.2	1.9	1.7	1.5	1.1
Tb	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.3	0.5	0.77
Lu	0.4	0.33	0.48	0.41	0.44	0.43
Σ REE	176.1	172.43	225.25	197.11	206.24	160.7

In Σ REE content, the REE content in the shales ranges from 172.43 and 225.68. The bulk REE normally reside in the clay fraction (silt or clay) and it has also been inferred that trivalent REE readily accommodated in most clay minerals enriched with alumina and ferric iron. The REEs were compared to the Post-Achaean Australian Standard (PAAS). The shales show slightly high LREE (light rare earth elements) enrichment and relatively low HREE (heavy rare earth elements).

Fig.3 Chondrite-normalised rare earth element plot for Shales of the Gongila Formation (normalising values after Sun and Mcdorrough , 1989).

Fig.4 Primitive Mantle normalised rare earth element plots for Shales of Gongila Formation.

The REE patterns of europium anomaly in sedimentary rocks provide important clues regarding source rock characteristics (Taylor and McLennan, 1985). Higher LREE/HREE ratios and negative Europium (Eu) anomalies are generally found in felsic rocks, where as the mafic rocks exhibit low LREE/HREE ratios and none or small Eu anomalies (Cullers, 1995). The positive Eu anomalies are generally found in Precambrian rocks (tonalite-tronjhemite-gneiss (TTG), granitoids, and quartz diorite). The TTG rocks exhibits very high LREE/HREE ratios and no or small positive positive Eu anomalies, and the positive anomaly resulted from hornblende-melt equilibria.

Table 2: Range of Elemental Ratios of Shales in the Study Area compared to Ratios in Similar Fractions Derived from Felsic Rocks, Mafic Rocks and Upper Continental Crust. (n=number of samples)

Elemental Ratios	Range of Sediments			
	Range of Shale (n=5)	Felsic Rocks	Mafic Rocks	UCC
Th/Sc	1.35-1.51	0.84-20.5	0.05-0.22	0.79
Th/Co	1.25-1.91	0.67-19.4	0.04-1.4	0.63
Th/Cr	0.23-0.27	0.13-2.7	0.018-0.046	0.13
Cr/Th	3.17-4.29	4.00-15	25-500	7.76
La/Sc	2.84-3.68	2.5-16.3	0.43-0.86	2.21

The shales of the Gongila Formation shows slightly high LREE/HREE ratios which suggests that they were mainly derived from Intermediate granitic source rocks. Ratios such as La/Sc are significantly different in felsic and basic rocks. The La/Sc ratios in the studied samples range between 2.84 and 3.68 and compared with those of the sediments derived from felsic and basic rocks (fine fraction) as well as the Upper Continental Crust (UCC).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This study have shown from the REE pattern, as well as other geochemical parameters like the La/Sc, Th/Sc, Th/Co, Th/Cr, and Cr/Th ratios, and La/Sc vs Th/Co plot, that the shales of the Turonian- Cenomanian Gongila sedimentary sequence were mainly derived from felsic source rocks. The REE patterns also suggest that these shales may be from intermediate granitic source rocks.

REFERENCES

- Adekeye, O. A. ,Akande, S.O. and Abimbola, A.F(2007); Preliminary Investigation of Rare Earth Element(REE) Composition of shales in the Oshoshun Formation exposed at the Shagamu quarry, Eastern Dahomey Basin, Southwestern Nigeria, *Journal of Mining and Geology*, .43(2) pp105-108
- Benkhelil, J., (1986); Benue Trough and Chain, *Geological Magazine* 119: 155-168.
- Carter, J.D., Barber, W., Tait, E.A., Jones, G.P., (1963). The Geology of part of Adamawa, Bauchi and Borno Provinces in the North Eastern Nigeria. *Bulletin 30, Geological Survey of Nigeria*, 30:1:108.
- Cullers, R., Lowe, D.R., Cox, R.L., (1995). The influence of sediment recycling and basement composition on evolution of mudrock chemistry in the southwestern United States: *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 59(14), 2919-2940.
- Cratchley, C. R., and Jones, J. P., (1965). An Interpretation of the Geology and Gravity Anomalies in the Benue Valley, Nigeria. Overseas Geol. Seiru. *Geophysics*. Paper 1, 1-26.
- Elderfield, H., Hawkesworth, C.J., Greaves, M.J., and Calvert, S.E., (1981). Rare earth element geochemistry of oceanic ferromanganese nodules and associated sediments, *Geochem. Cosmochem. Acta*, 45: 1231-1234.
- Falconer, J. D., (1911): *The Geology and Geography of Northern Nigeria*. Macmillan Press. 295p
- Glasby, G.P., Gwozdz, R., Kunzendorf, H., Friedrich, G., and Thijssen,T.(1987). The distribution of rare earth and minor elements in manganese nodules and sediments from the equatorial and S.W. Pacific, *Lithos*. 20: 97-113.

Gradstein, F., Ogg, J., Smith, A., (2004); *A Geological Time Scale 2004*. Cambridge University Press, United Kingdom .589pp.

Grant, N. K., (1971): South Atlantic, Benue Trough and Gulf of Guinea Cretaceous Triple Junction. *Bulletin of the geological Society of America*. 82: 2295-2298.

Guiraud, M.,(1993):Late Jurassic rifting-Early Cretaceous rifting and Later Cretaceous transpressional inversion in the Upper Benue Basin (NE Nigeria) *Bulletin des Centres de Recherches Exploration-Production ELF Aquitaine* 17 pp 371-383.

Hoffman, E. L.,(1992). Instrumental Neutron Activation in Geo-analysis; *Journal of Geochemical Exploration*, 44:297-319.

King, L. C., (1950): Outline and Distribution of Gondwanaland. *Geological Magazine*, 87:353-559.

Imagbe L.O and Davou, D.D.(2007); Sedimentary and Geochemical Characteristics of the Cenomanian – Turonian Carbonates of the Gongila Formation, Gongola Basin, Upper Benue Trough Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Applied Science* 25:91-98

Obaje N.G; Peason, M.J; Suh, C.E. and Dada, S.S (1999b); Organic Geochemical characterization of the Potential Hydrocarbon source Rocks in the Upper Benue Trough. *Journal of Mining and Geology*, 35 (2): 137-152.

Obaje, N.G; Ulu, O.K; Maigari, S.A and Abubakar, M.B. (2000); Sequence Stratigraphic and Paleoenvironmental Interpretations of Heterohelids from the Pindiga Formation Northeastern Benue Trough, Nigeria. *Journal of Mining and Geology*, 36 (2) 191 – 152.

Obi, G.C. (1998). Upper Cretaceous Gongila Formation in the Hawal Basin, North Eastern Benue Trough: A storm and wave dominated regressive shoreline complex. *Journal of African Earth Science*. 26 (4), 61-63.

Petters, S.W. (1982); Central West African Cretaceous-Tertiary Benthic Foraminifera and Stratigraphy. *Paeconographica* A. 179 1-104

Poppof, M., (1986); The Upper Cretaceous Gongila and Pindiga Formations, Northern Nigeria Subdivision, Age, Stratigraphic Correlation and Paleogeographic Implications. *Echoppe Geol. Helv. Besel*, 79. 263-343.

Wright, J. B., (1981); Review of the origin and evolution of the Benue Trough in Nigeria. *Earth Evolutionary Science*. 2, 9.

Zarboski, P.M. (1997); A Review of the Cretaceous System in Nigeria, *Africa Geoscience Reviews* 5 385-483

Zarboski, P.M. (2000). The Cretaceous and Paleocene transgressions in Nigeria and Niger. *Journal of Mining and Geology* 36, 155-175.

Zarboski, P. Ugodunlunwa, F. Idornigie, A., Nnabo, P and Ibe, K. (1998). Stratigraphy and structure of the Cretaceous Gongola basin, Northeastern Nigeria. *Bulletin des Centres de Recherches Exploration-Production. ELF-Aquitaine* 21 (for 1997), 153-185.

Received for Publication: 03/03/10

Accepted for Publication: 02/04/10

Corresponding Author

Imagbe, L.O

Department of Geology and Mining, University of Jos, P.M.B. 2084, JOS, NIGERIA.